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Books

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 2. Auflage 2018

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 3. Auflage 2020

Milestones in Analog and Digital Computing, Springer, 3rd edition 2020

Meilensteine der Rechentechnik, De Gruyter, 1. Auflage 2015

Konrad Zuse und die Schweiz, 1. Auflage 2012

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